

A GENERAL CLASSIFICATION OF THE MINT FAMILY IN KARAKALPAKSTAN

Nag‘metullaev Marat

Master’s student

Karakalpak State University after named Berdakh
Nukus, Uzbekistan

Abstract: In this article analyzing means that perennial grasses, shrubs and semi-shrubs belonging to the mint family are widespread in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and play an important role not only in the valley, but also in the flora of Uzbekistan.

Keywords— mint, flora, Lamiaceae, adaptation, environmental conditions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The flora of Karakalpakstan differs from other flora by its richness in many useful, medicinal, essential and ornamental plant species. Many plant species are widely used in medicine, cooking, gardening and other fields. However, the species, genera and families of useful plants in the flora of Uzbekistan have not yet been fully studied. Many species of local biodiversity plants have not yet found their place in people's daily lives or in some industries. Another fact is that of the more than 300,000 plant species in the world's flora, only about 2,500 are used to some degree in human daily life.

59 species of 26 genera of the Lamiaceae family grow in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (Table 1).

When analyzing the species belonging to the family of mint, it is distinguished by the large number of members of the

family Nepeta (9 species). In second place are Eremstachys (8 species), and in third place are Scutellaria and Phlomis (5 species) in terms of distribution.

In mountainous and foothill areas in early spring can be seen flowering and fertilization of plants belonging to the genus Salvia and Lagochilus (4 species). In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, there are only two species of Perovskia and Dracocephalum, and only one species of the remaining genera.

Of the 30 species of plants listed in the Red Data Book of Uzbekistan, only one species is Salvia margaritae Botsch in the flora of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. occurs.

In the flora of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, members of the Lamiaceae family have a special place due to their diversity and adaptation to different environmental conditions, as well as a number of medicinal properties.

Table 1. Species of the family Lamiaceae, distributed in the Republic of Karakalpakstan

№	Category name	Number of rounds	Total number of rounds %
1	Teucrium	1	1,7 %
2	Scutellaria	5	8,5 %
3	Drepanocaryum	1	1,7 %
4	Marrubium	1	1,7 %
5	Sideritis	1	1,7 %
6	Lophanthus	1	1,7 %
7	Nepeta	9	15,3 %
8	Dracocephalum	2	3,4 %
9	Lallemantia	1	1,7 %
10	Prunella	1	1,7 %
11	Eremstachys	8	13,5 %
12	Phlomis	5	8,5 %
13	Lamium	1	1,7 %
14	Lagochilus	4	6,8 %
15	Otostegia	1	1,7 %
16	Stachus	1	1,7 %
17	Chamespharos	1	1,7 %
18	Salvia	4	6,8 %

19	Perovskia	2	3,4 %
20	Ziziphora	1	1,7 %
21	Antonina	1	1,7 %
22	Clinopoduim	1	1,7 %
23	Origanum	1	1,7 %
24	Thymus	2	3,4 %
25	Lycopus	1	1,7 %
26	Mentha	2	3,4 %
	TOTAL; 26	59	100%

2. LIFESTYLE ANALYSIS

Analysis of the life forms of the Lamiaceae family in the Republic of Karakalpakstan showed that the main part of the plants belonging to this family are shrubs and semi-shrubs (Table 2).

Twenty-two members of the Peppermint family are perennial grasses found in the mountains and foothills. Nine of them are annual grasses, and there are no phanerophytes or therophytes in the family

Table 2. Lamiaceae is a species of species in the Republic of Karakalpakstan

№	Life form	Number of rounds	The ratio of the total number of species is in%
1	Phanerophytes (trees).	-	-
2	Hamefits (shrub, semi-shrub and liana).	28	47
3	Hemicryptophytes (perennial herbaceous plants).	22	37
4	Cryptophytes (root crops, bulbs).	-	-
5	Terofit (bir yillik o'simlik) lar.	9	0,1
Total:		59	100

3. GEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS

The analysis of plant species belonging to the family of mint of the Republic of Karakalpakstan revealed that the main

species are naturally distributed in the territory of the republic. (table 3)

Table 3. Regional analysis of the mint family

№	Category	Type	Beruni	Turtkul	Ellikhqala
1	Teurium	T.scordioides	+		+
2	Scutellaria	S.galericulata			+
		S.immaculata			+
		S.adenostegia			+
		S.ocellata	+		+

		S.comasa	+	+	+
3	Drepanocaryum	D.Severtzovii			+
4	Marrubium	M.alternidens			+
5	Sideritis	S.montana	+	+	+
6	Lophanthus	L.schtsharovskianus			+
7	Nepeta	N.subhastata			+
		N.podostachys			+
		N.kokanica			+
		N.Olgae	+	+	+
		N.cataria	+		+
		N.annonica			+
		N.micrantha			+
		N.santoana			+
		N.satureioides	+		+
8	Dracocephalum	D.imberbe	+		+
		D.integrifolium			+
9	Lallemantia	L.Royleana	+	+	+
10	Hypogomphia	H.turkistana		+	
11	Prunella	P.valgaris	+		+
12	Eremostachys	E.cordifolia	+		+
		E.Lehmanniana	+		+
		E.Agreni	+		+
		E.ferganensis		+	
		E.canescens	+		+
		E.nuda		+	
		E.integior	+		+
		E.speciosa	+		+
		E.pulchra	+		+
		E.codonocalyx	+	+	+
13	Phlomis	Ph.hycolenca		+	
		Ph.Severtzovii	+		+
		Ph.Daobovii	+		+
		Ph.alaica	+		+
		Ph.oreophilla	+		+
		Ph.Ostrovskiana	+		+
14	Lamium	L.amplexicaule	+	+	+
15	Lagochilus	L.Knorringianus	+		+
		L.Paulsenii	+		+
		L.hirsutissimus	+		+
		L.pubescens	+		+
16	Otastegia	O.Olgae	+	+	+
17	Stachys	S.silvatica	+		+
18	Chamaesphacos	Ch.ilicifolius	+	+	+
19	Salvia	S.Margaritae	+		+
		S.sclarea	+	+	+
		S.virgata	+		+
		S.deserta	+		+
20	Perovskia	P.angustifolia	+	+	+
		P.scrophulariifolia	+		+
21	Ziziphora	Z.brevicalyx	+		+
22	Antonina	A.debilis	+		+
23	Clinopodium	C.integereimum	+		+
24	Hyssopus	H.zeravschanicus		+	
25	Origanum	O.tytthantkum	+	+	+

26	Thymus	Th.zeravschanicus	+		
		Th.incertus	+		
27	Lycopus	L.curopolus	+	+	+
28	Mentha	M.arvensis	+		
		M.asiatica	+	+	+

Analysis of plant species belonging to the Mint family of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the steep regions showed that the main plant species are distributed in the hills and mountains. (Table 4).

Two species of the Scutellaria family are found in the hills, while four species of the same family grow in the mountains.

3 species of the family Nepeta grow on hills, 6 species in mountainous areas. Species of the genus Phlonis (Lamb), Salvia (Marmarak), which belong to the family of mint, are also important because they are widespread in the hills and mountains.

Table 4. Distribution across vertical regions

№	Category	№	Type	The desert	Adir	Mountain	Pasture
1	Scutellaria	1	S.immaculata	-	-	+	-
		2	S.adenostegia	-	+	+	-
		3	S.ocellata	-	-	+	-
		4	S.comasa	-	+	+	-
2	Drepanocaryum	5	D.Severtzovii	-	-	+	-
3	Sideritis	6	S.montana	-	+	+	-
4	Lophanthus	7	L.Schtschuraskianus	-	+	+	-
5	Nepeta	8	N.subhastata	-	-	+	-
		9	N.podostachys	-	+	+	-
		10	N.kokanica	-	+	+	-
		11	N.Olgae	-	+	+	-
		12	N.cataria	-	-	+	-
		13	N.santoana	-	-	+	-
		14	D.imberbe	-	+	+	-
6	Dracocephalum	15	D.integrifolium	-	+	+	-
7	Lallemantia	16	L.Royleana	+	-	+	-
8	Prunella	17	P.vulgaris	-	-	+	-
9	Eremostachys	18	E.cordifolia	-	+	+	-
		19	E.Lehmanniana	-	-	+	-
		20	E.Angreni	-	+	+	-
		21	E.canescens	+	-		-
		22	E.integior	-	+	+	-
		23	E.Speciosa	-	+	+	-
		24	E.codonacalyx	-	+	+	-
		25	Ph.Severtzovii	-	+	+	-
10	Phlonis	26	Ph.Drobovii	-	+	+	-
		27	Ph.alaica	-	+	+	-
		28	Ph.oreophila	-	+	+	-
		29	Ph.Ostrovskiana	-	+	+	-
		30	L.amplexicaule	+	-	+	-
11	Lamium	31	L.Knorringtonianus	-	+	+	-
12	Lagochikus	32	L.Paulsenii	-	+	+	-
		33	L.hirsutissimus	-	+	+	-
1	Stachys	34	S.silvatica	-	-	+	-

3							
1 4	Chamaesphacos	35	Ch.ilicifolius	+	-		-
1 5	Salvia	36	S.Margaritae	-	+	+	-
		37	S.virgata	-	+	+	-
		38	S.deserta	-	+	+	-
1 6	Perovskia	39	P.angustifolia	-	+	+	-
		40	P.scrophulariifolia	-	+	+	-
1 7	Ziziphora	41	Z.brevicalyx	-	+	+	-
1 8	Antonina	42	A.debilis	-	-	+	-
1 9	Clinopodium	43	C.integerrimum	-	-	+	-
2 0	Origanum	44	O.tythanthum	-	+	+	-
2 1	Thymus	45	Th.zeravshanicus	-	+	+	-
		46	Th.incertus	-	-	+	-
2 2	Mentha	47	M. asiatica	+	-	+	-

4. CONCLUSION

This means that perennial grasses, shrubs and semi-shrubs belonging to the mint family are widespread in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and play an important role not only in the valley but also in the flora of Uzbekistan.

5. REFERENCES

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